

Impact Resistance of Composite Fabric Based on Shear Thickening Gel

Muhammad Mudassar Naseer ✉

School of Mechanical and Vehicle Engineering,
Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Li Shiqiang ✉

Institute of Applied Mechanics,
Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Burhan Khalid

School of Mechanical Engineering,
Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Muhammad Yousaf Iqbal

School of Mechanical and Vehicle Engineering,
Zhejiang University of Technology, China

Rustam Tahami

School of Mechanical and Vehicle Engineering,
Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Shayan Ul Abidin

Department of Data Science,
Institute of Management Sciences (IMSciences), Pakistan

Article History:

Received: 20.03.2025 Revised: 11.04.2025 Accepted: 16.04.2025 Published: 17.04.2025

ABSTRACT:

In order to understand the impact resistance of shear thickened gel (STG) and find a simple test method for impact resistance, the composite fabric of shear thickened gel and warp knitted spacer fabric was prepared by impregnation and filling, and its performance was evaluated by bursting strength test and drop hammer impact test. The outcomes showed that the bursting strength, bursting elongation and bursting work of the samples prepared by impregnation method increased with the increase of shear thickening gel ratio, and the samples prepared by ethanol and gel dilution with the mass of 1:9 had the best performance. The two groups of composite materials prepared by immersion method and filling method showed an increase of 51% in energy absorption compared to the original sample in the drop hammer impact test 85% and 76 54%. The impact resistance of warp knitted spacer fabric with shear thickening gel is greatly improved. The use of the top burst test method can replace the drop hammer impact test for evaluating the impact resistance of fabrics.

Keywords: shear thickening gel, knitted interval fabric, impact resistance, energy absorption.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, people have paid increasing attention to the safety protection function of clothing [1-2]. The impact resistance performance is no longer limited to the protection requirements of some high-risk occupations, and the needs in daily life are gradually becoming more widespread. Careless falls of young children and elderly people may endanger their lives. Motorcycle riders are also prone to bumps and bruises. Self-protection is even more necessary when engaging in outdoor ice and snow sports, mountaineering, cycling, and other activities. Therefore, various types of protective materials and research continue to emerge.

Traditional protective gear on the market is mostly made of hard and heavy chemical synthetic products such as silicone and rubber, which are not easy to wear. A new type of flexible protective material, shear thickening fluid (STF), is composite with high-performance fabrics. Under high-speed impact, it exhibits the characteristics of an expanding plastic fluid, becoming viscous and hard, achieving the purpose of protecting the human body. It is widely used in military bulletproof and stab proof clothing [3]. In recent years, the appearance of shear thickening gel (STG) has made flexible protective materials start to be used in ski suits, cycling suits and motorcycle clothing [4].

STG, as a new type of material, is applied in protective products with properties similar to shear thickening fluids, and will exhibit shear thickening effects with increasing strain rates. However, shear thickened gel is not easy to leak and will not cause sedimentation and stratification under long-term standing, which is more suitable for the development of protective products. This shear thickening gel is placed on the inside of the soldier's helmet, which can reduce the impact force of bullets or fragments by 50% and protect the soldier's head. Wang et al. [5] studied the impact resistance of the material by combining shear thickened gel with polyurethane foam. Compared with the low-speed impact results, the higher the speed, the better the protective performance of shear thickened gel. STG behaves as a soft colloid without external forces and with minimal external forces, and its flexibility can meet the comfort requirements of clothing fabrics, making it suitable for developing protective clothing products [6].

Knitted interval fabrics are widely used in the field of protection due to their unique structure [7]. This 3D fabric is woven by a double needle bed Raschel machine, with two layers connected by spacer wires, forming a unique three-dimensional fabric structure that gives the fabric good energy absorption and buffering capabilities [8]. Compared with the production process of foam materials and adhesive laminated fabrics with similar performance, its production cost is low and it will not cause environmental pollution, especially the overall integrity of the fabric structure is better, which is widely used in various protective fields [9]. In order to produce flexible materials with better protective performance, Muthu Kumar et al. [10] studied and analyzed the compression and impact resistance of warp knitted spacer fabrics from a structural perspective. When subjected to external forces, the spacer fibers of the warp knitted spacer fabric play an important buffering role during the compression to lodging stage. 3D warp knitted spacer fabrics have more composite methods than two-dimensional fabrics.

In this paper, warp knitted spacer fabric is selected as the carrier and skeleton of gel to make gel more stable and easier to combine with clothing. At the same time, the three-dimensional multi-layer warp knitting spacing structure will greatly increase the area of shear thickening gel adhesion, facilitate composite, and enhance the overall cushioning performance of the material. In order to find a simple evaluation method and means for the impact resistance of materials, the buffering and energy absorption of the samples were evaluated through bursting strength and drop hammer impact experiments, providing reference for the testing of material impact resistance and guidance for the development of related clothing.

MATERIAL

Anhydrous ethanol; Knitted interval fabric (100% polyester, commercially available); Shear thickened gel (strain rate sensitive material type I, response shear rate $\leq 0.1 \text{ s}^{-1}$). YG0650 electronic fabric strength tester, Instron dynatup 9250 HV fully digital drop hammer impact tester, JSM-7500F scanning electron microscope, ZKXFB-2 electric vacuum drying oven, P-A0 rolling mill.

METHODS

Immersion Method

The shear thickened gel is easily soluble in anhydrous ethanol to prepare composite materials. Weigh/measure the shear thickened gel and anhydrous ethanol in a certain proportion, and place them in a beaker until the gel is completely dissolved. Multiple groups of samples were prepared by changing the ratio of anhydrous ethanol to shear thickened gel. The warp knitted spacer fabric of a certain size is put into the above solution for uniform soaking, and then taken out. The solution is evenly distributed to the fabric with a rolling car, and the excess rolling solution is removed. The second dipping and second rolling make the gel fully enter the fabric. Dry in a vacuum drying oven at $(55 \pm 5) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours to remove ethanol and bubbles.

Filling Method

The 3D structure of the warp knitted spacer fabric is used as the "skeleton" of the shear thickening gel. First, the gel is kneaded into sheets and placed on the warp knitted spacer fabric, and a certain pressure is applied by the rolling car. Under the continuous stress, the gel is pressed into the pores of the warp knitted spacer fabric. Add gel repeatedly until the spacer wire is filled evenly. Place it in a $(55 \pm 5) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ vacuum drying oven for 2h to remove bubbles in gel and increase the rheology of gel by heating up, so that the gel is evenly dispersed. In order to ensure the shape of shear thickened gel is stable for a long time, silicone rubber can be coated on the surface of the fabric, and thermoplastic polyurethane elastomer rubber (TPU) material can be bonded on it for composite packaging.

Breaking Strength Tests

Conduct experiments using a bursting strength tester according to GB/T 19976-2005 "Determination of bursting strength of textiles - Steel ball method". After placing the prepared composite material in an environment with a temperature of $(20 \pm 3) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $(55 \pm 3) \%$ for 24 hours, cut it into circular specimens with a diameter of 80 mm. Use a steel ball with a diameter of 20 mm, select a gripper diameter of 25 and 45 mm, and perform top breaking at different rates. Test each sample 5 times, record the top breaking strength and elongation, and calculate the average value. If there is slippage during the testing process, the experiment is invalid.

Buffering Performance Test

After placing the composite materials prepared in Step 3.1 and 3.2 in an environment with a temperature of $(20 \pm 3) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $(55 \pm 3) \%$ for 24 hours, according to GB/T 21189-2007 "Inspection of Pendulum Impact Testing Machines for Plastic Simply Supported Beams, Cantilever Beams, and Tensile Impact Testing", 10 cm square test samples were cut from different parts of the composite materials for experimentation. Five valid samples are tested in each group, and the experimental data is recorded to calculate the average value. The buffering performance of the material is evaluated by comparing the energy absorbed, instantaneous velocity, and deflection curves.

Using the Instrumental 9250HV fully digital drop hammer impact testing machine (as shown in Figure 1), a semi cylindrical hammer head was selected to simulate low-speed blunt impacts in daily scenarios for the experiment.

Figure 1. Digital Drop Hammer Impact Testing Machine

In order to ensure that the sample is completely destroyed, the total impact energy of the drop hammer is set at 20 J, and the cushioning performance of the warp knitted spacer fabric before and after adding gel is tested [11-12]. In the experiment, the device sensors record the speed changes, and by calculating the speed difference, the changes in load deflection and the energy absorbed by the material during the impact process are calculated based on energy conservation. Due to the flexible nature of the prepared composite material, preliminary experiments were conducted to simulate the moment when a person falls while wearing clothing and comes into contact with a hard object. Mixed wood boards were used as fixed auxiliary support materials for impact testing. The sample preparation method is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Preparation Method of Sample

Place the fabric on top of the board and clamp it with a pneumatic clamp. The hammer head will first come into contact with the sample during the falling process, and the sample will act as a buffer before the board is damaged. If there is slippage during the testing process, the experiment is invalid. When processing the data, subtract the data of separately measured plates for statistics, and compare the cushioning effect of gel composite fabrics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

By observing the composite samples prepared by different methods, it is found that the gel is evenly attached to the fiber surface, making the composite fabric shinier than the original. The spacer fibers on the cross section are very obvious and play a role in supporting and connecting the upper and lower layers. The surface of the sample still retains the mesh structure of the warp knitted spacer fabric, which has a certain degree of breathability. At this time, the composite material is mainly gel, and its shape is more stable than pure gel. Warp knitted spacer fabric plays a role in stabilizing the shape. The observation section shows that the warp knitted spacer fabric as the base fabric is completely wrapped with gel, and its surface is smooth without pores. The microstructure of composite fabric samples prepared by different methods is shown in Figure 3, which provides a clearer understanding of their structural differences.

Figure 3. Electron Microscopy Images of Composite Fabric Samples Prepared by Different Methods ($\times 25$)

The gel of the sample prepared by impregnation is uniformly attached to the fiber, and the fabric maintains its original air permeability; The structure of fiber and fabric cannot be seen in the sample prepared by filling method under the electron microscope, and the gel completely encloses the fiber. Top pole operating speed. The ejector rod with a steel ball diameter of 20 mm and a holder diameter of 25 mm are selected. The specimen containing gel is tested by changing the ejector rod speed. The results of the bursting test under different operating speeds of the ejector rod are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental Results of Top Breaking under Different Operating Speeds of the Top Rod

m (ethanol) : m (gel)	Surface density ($\text{g} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$)	Mass fraction of gel (%)	Top rod speed (mm $\cdot \text{min}^{-1}$)	Bursting strength		Top breaking displacement	
				Mean (N)	Change rate (%)	Mean (mm)	Change rate (%)
Original state	167.2	—	300	436.6	—	10.1	—
			750	400.2	8.34	9.33	7.51
			1500	365.8	16.22	9.16	9.42
20 : 80	362.3	53.86	300	471.8	—	11.54	—
			750	414.1	12.21	10.32	10.58
			1500	391.7	16.96	9.70	15.93
10 : 90	569.2	70.50	300	447.5	—	12.27	—
			750	428.8	4.20	11.67	5.05
			1500	415.7	7.15	11.70	4.73

As shown in Table 1, with the increase of the top rod speed, the top breaking strength and top breaking displacement of the same sample decrease. All three samples, including the original

sample, showed the same pattern. This is because the faster the speed of the top rod, the greater the energy, and the sample has no time to react and transfer the external force it receives. Therefore, the area of the external force is small and the external force is concentrated, resulting in smaller results. Since the impact speed of human body is relatively fast, and the shear thickened gel can play a better role in buffering at high speed, the ejector speed is selected as 1500 mm/min in the following experiment. Clamp diameter. The experimental results of top rupture under different clamp diameters are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Experimental Results of Top Rupture under Different Clamp Diameters

m (ethanol) : m (gel)	Surface density ($\text{g} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$)	Mass fraction of gel (%)	Bursting strength (N)		Breaking displacement (mm)	
			25 mm	45 mm	25 mm	45 mm
Original state	167.2	—	365.8	352.2	9.16	12.32
20 : 80	362.3	53.86	391.7	370.4	9.70	15.13
10 : 90	569.2	70.50	415.7	378.7	11.70	16.10

As shown in Table 2, the measured bursting strength decreased with the use of clamps of different caliber sizes, but the bursting displacement increased significantly. This is because the larger the diameter of the gripper, the larger the effective area during bursting, and the weaker links it encounters, resulting in a smaller bursting force. The larger the area of action during the toppling process, the greater the toppling displacement. In order to reduce the weak links during the bursting process, a clamp with a diameter of 25 mm was used in the following experiment. With the increase of shear thickening gel ratio, the bursting strength and displacement of samples increase. However, the mass fraction of gel is less than 70%, the bursting strength and bursting displacement have little change, and the mass fraction of shear thickened gel needs to be more than 70%. The typical curve model of top breaking force top breaking displacement was obtained through analysis. The entire process, from the contact of the steel ball with the fabric, the stretching and tightening of the fabric, the breaking of the fabric, and the decrease in force, presents an approximately triangular curve. When the fabric breaks, the maximum strength reached is called the bursting strength, and the elongation at this time is called the bursting displacement. The energy consumed during the bursting process is called the bursting work.

Geometrically, the value of the top breaking energy corresponds to the area contained in the top breaking force top breaking displacement curve and the horizontal displacement, and the accurate value is calculated through integration. Due to the similarity in the shape of the bursting curves of each group of samples, they are simplified to the area of a triangle for comparison. By calculating the area of the triangle and dividing the product of the bursting force and bursting displacement by 2, the bursting power can be estimated. According to Newton's third law and the law of conservation of energy, the force displayed by the instrument during the bursting process is the magnitude of the force exerted by the steel ball on the specimen; The energy of the top breaking work is converted from mechanical energy to kinetic energy that destroys the internal fibers of the specimen, strain energy, and frictional energy consumed between the specimen and the clamping component. Among them, the energy that causes deformation and failure of the sample structure, namely strain energy, is the main one. Therefore, the energy consumed by the equipment is basically proportional to the energy absorbed by the fabric. By comparing the bursting power, it can be used as a reference for the energy absorbed by the sample during the bursting process.

By calculating the bursting work under different gel ratios at the ejector rod speed of 1500 mm/min, it can be seen that the energy absorbed by other composite samples in the bursting process is increased to varying degrees compared with the original sample, except for the samples impregnated with m (ethanol) : m (gel) 1:1, which proves that adding a certain proportion of shear thickening gel to the composite can improve its protective performance. Especially in the high proportion of gel content, the bursting work increases significantly.

In order to verify the results of bursting test, the original sample was impregnated with a mixture of m (ethanol) : m (gel) of 2 : 8 to obtain the impregnated sample. Four sets of samples were used as experimental objects, including board, board + warp knitted interval original sample, board + warp knitted interval impregnated sample, and board + warp knitted interval filled sample. The drop hammer impact test was conducted, and the instantaneous velocity and deflection curves are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Relationship Curve between Instantaneous Velocity and Sample Deflection

Figure 4 shows that the instantaneous velocity measured with the addition of cushioning material decreases significantly with the increase of deflection, indicating that the three groups of samples with added warp knitted spacer fabric have all played a good buffering role. The slope of velocity, also known as acceleration, reflects the force acting on the hammer head at this moment. Simple board group, slightly slows down but quickly accelerates again after the board is damaged; The other groups added cushioning materials of warp knitted spacer fabric on the board, and remained in a deceleration state when the deflection reached the edge of the range, showing a trend of continued deceleration, indicating that the hammer head was subjected to significant resistance at this time. Although the curves of several samples with added buffering materials basically overlap in the range of deflection less than 10 mm, and the difference is not significant, as the deflection of the material increases, the instantaneous velocity difference between each group of samples widens. Therefore, the buffering effect can be evaluated by comparing the slope size. To sum up, the buffering performance is ranked as warp knitting interval filling sample, warp knitting interval immersion sample, and warp knitting interval as is. The addition of gel has played a certain buffer role. Figure 5 shows the relationship curve between energy absorption and deflection of the sample, exhibiting a pattern similar to the instantaneous velocity deflection curve.

Figure 5. Energy Absorption and Sample Deflection Curve

At a deflection of 18.4 mm, the energy absorbed by several sets of samples, including the original sheet, sheet + warp knitted interval, sheet + warp knitted interval impregnated sample, and sheet + warp knitted interval filled sample, were 10.97, 12.59, 13.43, and 13.83 J, respectively. Comparing the energy absorbed by the removed board, it can be seen that the absorbed energy is in the order of filled sample group, impregnated sample group, and original sample group. The immersed sample group absorbed 0.84 J more energy than the original sample group, and the filled sample group absorbed 1.24 J more energy than the original sample group. Both groups absorbed 51.85% and 76.54% more energy in the drop hammer impact experiment compared to the original sample group, respectively. Due to the fact that the mass per unit area of the warp knitted interval filled sample is much larger than that of the warp knitted interval impregnated sample (2526.4 and 362.3 g/m², respectively), the warp knitted interval impregnated sample is more suitable for wearing impact resistant materials.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the bursting and drop hammer impact tests were carried out on the composite materials of shear thickened gel and warp knitted spacer fabric, and the application of shear thickened gel in fall resistant composite materials and the test and evaluation methods of fall resistant materials were discussed. The results of bursting test show that the bursting power, bursting strength and bursting displacement of warp knitted spacer fabric and warp knitted spacer composite fabric prepared by impregnation method increase with the increase of the proportion of shear thickened gel under a certain ejector speed and clamping caliber. The results of the drop hammer impact test showed that the protective performance of the composite materials prepared by the filling method and impregnation method was greatly improved. The energy absorbed by the two methods in the drop hammer impact test increased by 76.54% and 51.85%, respectively, compared to the original sample. The results of the top breaking experiment are consistent with those of the drop hammer impact experiment, so the top breaking experiment can replace the drop hammer impact experiment for impact resistance testing.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Nayak, S. Houshyar, and R. Padhye, "Recent trends and future scope in the protection and comfort of fire-fighters' personal protective clothing," *Fire Science Reviews*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–19, Dec. 2014, doi: [10.1186/s40038-014-0004-0](https://doi.org/10.1186/s40038-014-0004-0).
- [2] G. Natarajan and C. Hurren, "Critical properties of cotton, UHMWPE, and para-aramid blended fabrics for protective clothing applications," *The Journal of The Textile Institute*, pp. 1–10, 2025. [DOI not available].
- [3] Z. Lu, Y. Xu, and B. Sun, "Progress in shear thickening fluid study and its application in anti-impact and cushion areas," *Zhendong yu Chongji*, vol. 38, no. 17, pp. 128–136, 2019. [DOI not available].
- [4] M.-K. Chan, P.-L. Li, K.-L. Yick, J. Yip, and S.-P. Ng, "Exploration of Textile–Silicone Composites and Materials for Personal Impact-Resistant Protection," *Materials*, vol. 17, no. 6, p. 1439, 2024, doi: [10.3390/ma17061439](https://doi.org/10.3390/ma17061439).
- [5] Y. Wang, X. Gong, and S. Xuan, "Study of low-velocity impact response of sandwich panels with shear-thickening gel cores," *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 27, no. 6, p. 065008, 2018, doi: [10.1088/1361-665X/aac7d2](https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-665X/aac7d2).
- [6] D. Banerjee, J. H. Lew, and P. F. Luckham, "On the rheological properties of silica–Polyethylene oxide dispersions: Shake gels I the effect of polymer concentration and temperature," *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, vol. 703, p. 135194, 2024, doi: [10.1016/j.colsurfa.2020.125194](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2020.125194).

- [7] E. Tang et al., "Mechanical behavior of STF impregnation and anti-impact performances of Kevlar and UHMPWEF fabric impregnations," *Composite Structures*, vol. 341, p. 118228, 2024, doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.118228](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2022.118228).
- [8] Y. Yang and H. Hu, "Spacer fabric-based exuding wound dressing—Part I: Structural design, fabrication and property evaluation of spacer fabrics," *Textile Research Journal*, vol. 87, no. 12, pp. 1469–1480, 2017, doi: [10.1177/0040517516657291](https://doi.org/10.1177/0040517516657291).
- [9] Y. Tan, Y. Ma, and Y. Li, "Warp-knitted spacer fabric flexible composites with high stability and low-velocity impact resistance infused by flock-reinforced shear thickening gel," *Textile Research Journal*, vol. 93, no. 17–18, pp. 4246–4258, 2023, doi: [10.1177/00405175231171744](https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175231171744).
- [10] N. Muthu Kumar, G. Thilagavathi, and S. Periasamy, "Development and characterization of warp knitted spacer fabrics for helmet comfort liner application," *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, vol. 51, no. 2_suppl, pp. 2053S–2070S, 2022, doi: [10.1177/1528083720939215](https://doi.org/10.1177/1528083720939215).
- [11] G. Li et al., "The effects of orientation angle of bamboo strands on the properties of bamboo oriented strand board," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 98, p. 111476, 2024, doi: [10.1016/j.jobbe.2023.111476](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2023.111476).
- [12] Z. X. Yu et al., "Impact resistance properties of bamboo scrimber," *Journal of Northeast Forestry University*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 46–48, 2012.

